

Information and Communication Technology Competence and Utilization for Services Delivery by Librarians in Adamawa State Academic Libraries, Nigeria

Fadimatu Sa'ad Laido
Jiril Aminu Library, Federal Polytechnic Mubi,
Adamawa State, Nigeria
fatimatusaad2019@gmail.com

Fatima L. Ibrahim
Department of Library and Information Science,
University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

Yahaya Aliyu
Department of Library and Information Science,
University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

Abstract

Keywords
 ICT,
 Competence,
 Utilization,
 and
 Academic
 Libraries,
 Services
 Deliver

Introduction: The study analyzed ICT competence and utilization for service delivery by librarians in Adamawa State academic libraries, Nigeria. It aimed to determine the extent of ICT competence among librarians, ICT utilization in service delivery, and the challenges inhibiting ICT competence in academic libraries in Adamawa State.

Method: The survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 116 library staff from three selected academic libraries in Adamawa State, using total enumeration sampling. Data were collected using a questionnaire and checklist, and analyzed with descriptive statistics, including frequency count and percentage scores.

Results/Findings: The findings revealed that ICT competence of librarians in academic libraries in Adamawa State is low. Similarly, ICT utilization for service delivery is also low. Challenges inhibiting ICT competence and service delivery include inadequate ICT facilities, lack of skilled staff, insufficient telecommunication facilities, low staff computer literacy, inadequate funds, resistance to ICT adoption, and frequent changes in ICT.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the low extent of ICT competence and utilization significantly affects service delivery in academic libraries in Adamawa State.

Recommendations: The study recommends that library management should create awareness on the use of ICT for effective service delivery and provide adequate ICT facilities, skilled staff, telecommunication facilities, computer literacy training, sufficient funds, and address staff resistance to ICT adoption and frequent changes in ICT.

Introduction

Emerging technologies have been integrated into the library and information services for effective and efficient library services delivery (Omehia, Anthonia, Okwu, Emmanuel, Nsirim & Onyema, 2021). This however cannot be effective if librarians lack Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) competencies to utilize them. Skills are essential for excellent job performance and libraries as a matter of necessity should prepare librarians for emerging technologies to enable them handle different jobs as required by different ICT tasks (Oyedokun, Oyewumi, Akanbi & Laaro, 2018). The level of ICT competencies required vary from one position to another depending on the tasks and duties involved. Obotu, Chukwuka and Gambo (2019) regard Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as the acquisition, analysis, manipulation, storage and distribution of information; and the design and provision of equipment and software for these purposes. Omosor and Nelson (2017) defined ICT as computers and other technologies that are used in the acquisition, organization, storage and dissemination of information in libraries. No doubt, ICT is a catalyst for generating, processing, storing and disseminating information (Kwofie, Aigbavboa & Thwala, 2020).

ICT competencies of librarians are those technological and or computer skills and knowledge required by librarians to be able to fully exploit information services in the wake of new technology. Oyedokun, Oyewumi, Akanbi & Laaro (2018) viewed ICT competencies of library staff to be those relevant skills and knowledge acquired by the library staff which enable them to fully exploit information search, retrieval, and delivery using electronic format. It is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities at a level of expertise, sufficient to be able to perform

appropriately and professionally a given task in a work place. Competence is synonymous with skills and therefore is used interchangeably in this study.

Ademodi and Adepoju (2019) studied the possession of skills and competencies in the use of computer with a population of thirty academic librarians from which a sample of twenty-four was drawn. The data were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages. They found that 87.5% of librarians were computer literate. They also found that the most commonly reported skill was to navigate and explore the internet. Ojiegbe (2010) investigated the ICT competencies of library staff in the University of Abuja, FCT and University of Jos, Plateau State. Simple random sampling was used and the instrument used for data collection was questionnaires which were analyzed using percentages and mean scores. Findings revealed that most of the library staff in university libraries performed Microsoft Word based tasks like typing and printing of documents and could provide online searches using the internet but could not perform effective professional library related duties using ICT. It was stressed that Staff needed ICT competencies in the areas that can assist them to handle professional related duties, like internet skills, mastery of library software and technical skills.

Globally, libraries are dedicated to being socially responsible by contributing services that reach people in all works of life regardless of their social status, thereby bridging the information gaps through service delivery to people in the society (Vincent, Ikonne, & Ohwofasa, 2023). Academic libraries exist in many countries across the world including Nigeria and are often considered essential part of an educated and literate populace. Services delivery by employees in libraries is fundamental to the quality of education.

Since academic libraries are saddled with the responsibility of providing free access to a wide range of resources, including books, magazines, newspapers and electronic resources such as e-books, audiobooks, and online databases. This allows people to learn about a variety of subjects and keep up with current happenings around them (Vincent, Ikonne & Ohwofasa, 2023).

According to Madu (2010) service delivery in libraries is the sum total of all library activities aimed at facilitating the use of the library and its resources. It is the activity of a librarian in an academic library within and outside available resources to provide answers to user's queries and meet their information needs. Alabi, and Sani (2021) opined that academic libraries are veritable information providers that render strategic services and find new ways to serve patrons effectively and efficiently. Mbofung and Popoola (2014) described library service delivery as that which involves individuals, who have expectations of the library and information science professionals in such ways as how they relate and behave towards the users, colleagues, their organizations and the entire society.

The convergence of ICT in academic libraries has brought about the maximum utilization of all the technologies that enable the handling of information of various formats within the library. Elisha (2006) identified a limited use and deployment of ICT across Nigerian libraries, according to the study, libraries used ICT to assist people to gain access to the materials, and to offer online reference services. Partridge and Munro, (2010) identified skills in the following areas: communication, management, collaboration, information management, leadership, marketing, project management, and community engagement. According to Mahadeva and Prasad (2016) cited in Chanchinmawia and Verma (2017) IL is a skill, ability, expertise, capability and

competency of a person that makes him able to find the right information from the right source. Zurkowski, the president of the Information Industry Association of United State coined the term "Information Literacy" in 1974. He introduced the concept of information literacy in a proposal to the United States national commission on libraries and information science as "people trained in the application of information resources to their work can be called information literates. They have learned techniques and skills for utilizing the wide range of information tools as well as primary sources in moulding information solutions to their problems" (Zurkowski, 1974).

Furthermore, a librarian should be innovative, adaptable, and flexible and be an active learner. The pervasiveness of digital technologies in daily life is fundamentally changing the way librarian's access, use and manages knowledge. Librarians need to process complex information which requires that they think critically and systematically to take decisions in different forms of evidence. Librarians will also have to constantly update their knowledge and skills to be in tandem with rapid technical change at their workplaces. More importantly, in order to leverage the new opportunities that digital technologies are presenting in many areas, individuals have to develop the right set of skills to make a meaningful use of these technologies. Omekwu (2008) identified basic knowledge of computers and their capabilities; competency with search engines; internet facilities; e-mail; internet navigator tools, web browsers and web file formats; database software; internet development and management know-how. Krishnan (2011) included creativity and innovation skills, media literacy, ICT literacy as well as flexibility and adaptability skills. The skills aforementioned are necessary for the utilization of emerging technologies in library and information services and that necessitates why this study investigates

the ICT competence of librarians for service delivery in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence and utilization by librarians usually lead to effective information service delivery. However, preliminary observation by the researcher showed that Information and Communication Technologies facilities in academic libraries in Adamawa State, Nigeria seem not to be in use and covered with dust, showing sign of abandonment. Furthermore, research from the literatures, revealed that factors influencing service delivery in libraries include: availability of information resources, accessibility and utilization of information resources by users, technological adaptation, financial resources and infrastructure. However, here are some listed major challenges against service delivery in academic libraries in Adamawa, lack of infrastructural facilities, inadequate qualified numbers of staff (Librarians), erratic power supply and lack of funds among many others.

It might be possible that these factors may not be effective on their own without good ICT skills. Therefore, ICT skills could however be significant factors that may influence service delivery in academic library in Adamawa State, Nigeria. This has further been attested by the study conducted by Abbas (2014) who uncovered that librarians lack the requisite expertise to maneuver the ICT facilities and navigate into the wealth of information resources available on the web and many general and specialized databases were never utilized by the librarians to deliver, provide and disseminate information to their clientele. Majority of the academic library staff lack ICT competence. Studies have consistently reported inadequate levels of ICT competence as one of the major problems facing libraries in Nigeria as they move into the 21st century.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study determined the:

1. The extent of ICT competence of librarians in *Adamawa State* academic libraries, Nigeria
2. ICT utilization for service delivery by librarians in *Adamawa State* academic libraries, Nigeria
3. Challenges inhibiting service delivery in academic libraries in Adamawa State.

Literature Review

Study carried out by Atte, and Ezra (2016) on Essential Competencies for Effective Information Service Delivery in Nigerian University Libraries, the result shows that, competencies level of the librarians in information technology for the provision of library and information service delivery. It indicates that the respondents were competent in Microsoft Word (words processing skills) with a mean score of 3.4453, e-mail management skills with a mean score of 3.4234 and using an integrated library system (virtual/Alice for windows) have the third highest mean score of 3.3212. The least of the competencies level of the librarians in information technology in the libraries studied were troubleshooting technology with a mean score of 2.3212, web development with a mean score of 2.3431 and blogging with a mean score of 2.3723. In overall, it could be said that the respondents are not competent in information technology sampling because majority of the information technology competencies options, respondents were found not to be competent.

This implies that they have not been providing library and information service delivery as being expected by their patrons especially in this technological era. It is not surprising because of the dynamic nature of technology which is constantly creating the need for new skills. This is in agreement with Tanloet and

Twamsuk (2010) who noted that in order to adopt these developments to library work and catch up with the technological advances, information professionals must learn to acquire various roles, knowledge, competencies and skills. Also, development of professional competencies enables us to work efficiently and survive in the world of libraries and information services. Accordingly, training and retraining of library staff is very essential for effective and efficient library and information service delivery in the Adamawa State Libraries.

Study conducted by Osuchukwu, Obuezie and Ogwuche (2017) shows that more number of staff utilized ICT facilities weekly and bi-monthly at 56.7%, respectively while 46.6% utilized it weekly and when they have office work. Others are daily utilized at 50% and once a semester at 11%. This shows that greater number of staff utilized the ICT section of the library in Madonna University. A computer performs processing operations on data and is used to store and retrieve information process transaction (charging and discharging), sort, data, etc. Since the central processing unit (CPU) or the computer has a definitive amount of data capacity; it requires additional storage media, such as magnetic disk and tape, and audio tape.

A disk is the most common auxiliary storage device. Telecommunications facilitates the transfer or communication of data and information technology in the libraries. Basically, information technology provides for full organizational structure (i.e. to provide enhanced users satisfaction. cost effectiveness, integration, faster, and simpler programmed, rapid responses, and operational procedures). Mamman (2015) posited that the consequences of not utilizing ICTs in tertiary institution libraries are that they will deny users access to the full range of resources available through newer technologies and their services will not meet the needs of users. As a result, users may

not be satisfied. Similarly, they would not be able to achieve self-actualization or their life goals. Therefore, utilization of ICTs in tertiary institution libraries will enhance the quality of their operations and services and lead to users' satisfaction. Another study conducted by Aba, Beetseh and Ogban (2015) revealed that 37.78% had received Internet training from external sources. The Internet skill of 44.44% was rated average. Only 22% used the Internet daily and 87.41 % claimed that digital libraries had greatly enhanced their academic performance. Majority of 51.11% used Internet facilities outside the University mainly for research and education activities. Problems encountered included longtime to view or download web pages and insufficient computers. The study revealed that the use of Internet had led to decreased in the use of traditional library facilities but only 94 % were fully satisfied with the Internet facilities. A large majority of 92.96% were of the opinion that proper guidance of students in the use of e-resource was needed.

Ikegwuro (2017) affirms that in academic library Internet is applied to provide easy access to current information and convenient information exchange. Internet is an abbreviation for International Network. It is not a single Network but a collection of computers worldwide through a system of connection that use the standard Internet Protocol Suite (TCP/IP) to serve billions of users worldwide. The application of Internet in academic libraries has tremendously changed the management of resources or housekeeping operations as well as the way services are delivered. The Internet holds great potentials in libraries; its services are largely used in housekeeping operations, like acquisition, cataloguing, circulation control, serials management etc. The Internet can be used to deliver the information needs of the users in academic libraries.

Mamman (2015) opined that despite its vitality in library parlance and its potentials for enhancing services and operations, there are obstacles which hamper effective utilization of ICTs in libraries. These obstacles, which generally hinge on facilities, skills acquisition and planning, comprise the following: lack of funds/economic barriers, lack of ICT infrastructure, poor and inadequate telecommunication facilities, poor level of computer literacy, low level of ICT skills, lack of functional ICT policy/strategy, resistance to change, cultural factors, etc. Finance plays a critical role in ensuring the availability and utilization of ICT facilities in libraries. But, sadly enough, this appears to be the greatest challenge for most libraries. Mole (2014) believed that efficient use of information technology is a key to providing access to information in reference services.

He further stated that a big challenge is now facing librarians in the area of utilizing these new technologies to provide reference, information as well as to give proper service delivery and give library users improved access to the world's reference sources. This implies that librarians should not only be restricted to printed sources in provision of services but should include other technologies that will enhance speedy and accurate dissemination of information to his clientele. Information

services delivered in academic libraries include library orientation and instruction.

Research Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for this study. The researcher used self-designed questionnaire and checklist to collect data from one hundred and sixteen (116) library staff made up of both professionals and para-professionals in the three selected academic libraries in Adamawa State, Nigeria namely; Federal Polytechnic Mubi Library, Adamawa State College of Education Hong Library and Adamawa State University Mubi Library. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage scores for the research questions, presented in tables

Data Analysis and Results

A total of 116 copies of questionnaire were administered to respondents in the three Academic libraries in Adamawa state, Nigeria. Out of these numbers one hundred and four (104) were completed, returned and found usable, giving 89.7% valid rate, while, twelve 12 copies of the questionnaire were invalid representing 10.3% as non-response rate, and the analysis was based on the 104 respondents.

Research Question One: What is the extent of ICT competence of librarians in academic libraries?

Table 1: ICT Competence of Librarians in Academic Libraries

S/N	Statement	HE	ME	LE	UN	Remark
1	What extent do you operate computers in your library for service delivery?	11(11%)	17(16%)	49(47%)	27(26%)	Low extent
2	What extent do you proficient use computer applications such as word processing, spreadsheet and email for service delivery?	21(20%)	13(13%)	51(49%)	19(18%)	Low extent

3	What extent do you comfortable use library management system and other specialized software for service delivery?	9(9%)	11(10%)	61(59%)	23(22%)	Low extent
4	What extent do you search the internet for service delivery?	10(10%)	12(11%)	63(61%)	19(18%)	Low extent
5	To what extent do you consider yourself to have a high level of ICT competence for service delivery?	11(10%)	10(10%)	71(68%)	12(12%)	Low extent
Total Average		62/5	63/5	295/5	100/5	Low extent
		12.4	12.6	59	20	
		(12%)	(12.1%)	(56.7%)	(19.2%)	

High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Low Extent (LE), and Undecided (UN)

Table 1 shows extent ICT competence of library staff in academic libraries in Adamawa State, with what extent do you operate computers in your library for service delivery where 49(47%) with low extent, 27(26%) respondents were undecided, 17(16%) respondents with moderate extent, while 11(11%) respondents with high extent. This implies that majority of the respondents were with low extent in terms of operating computers in their library for service delivery. Items two shows proficient use of computer applications such as word processing, spreadsheet and email for service delivery where 51(49%) at low extent, 21(20%) of the respondent at high extent, and 19(18%) respondent was undecided while 13(13%) at moderate extent. This shows that majority of the respondents use computer applications such as word processing, spreadsheet and email for service delivery at low extent in their libraries. Items three is on the use of library management system and other

specialized software for service delivery where, 61(59%) low extent, while 23(22%) were undecided respectively 11(10%) with moderate extent 9(9%) of the respondents indicated high extent on the use of library management system and other specialized software for service delivery. Responses on staff competency in search of internet for service delivery where 63(61%) low extent and 19(18%) were undecided, 10(10%) of the respondent indicated high extent for searching the internet for service delivery, 12(11%) to moderate extent. Finally, responses view on extent do you consider yourself to have a high level of ICT competence for service delivery where 71(68%) low extent and 12(12%) undecided, 11(10%) of the respondent show high extent on high level of ICT competence for service delivery, 10(10%) moderate extent. This shows that majority of the respondents are of the opinion that ICT competence of library staff in academic libraries in Adamawa State were low extent.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of ICT use on service delivery by librarians?

Table 2: The ICT Utilization on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries

S/N	Statements	HE	ME	LE	UN	Remark
1	To what extent do you utilize ICT for reference services?	11(10%)	9(9%)	61(59%)	23(22%)	Low extent
2	To what extent do you utilize ICT for current awareness services?	10(10%)	11(10%)	71(68%)	12(12%)	Low extent
3	To what extent do you utilize ICT for charging and discharging of materials?	13(12%)	10(10%)	59(57%)	22(21%)	Low extent
4	To what extent do you utilize ICT for inter-library loan services?	13(13%)	21(20%)	51(49%)	19(18%)	Low extent
5	To what extent do you utilize ICT for user education services?	11(11%)	17(16%)	49(47%)	27(26%)	Low extent
Total Average		58/5 11.6 (11.1%)	68/5 13.6 (13%)	291/5 58.2 (56%)	103/5 20.6 (19.9%)	Low extent

104

High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Low Extent (LE), and Undecided (UN)

Table 2 present the responses view on ICT utilization on service delivery in Academic Libraries where 61(59%) of the respondents were utilizing ICT for their reference services in academic library under study at the high extent, 23(22%) of the responses were undecided, while 11(10%) high extent and 9(9%) of the respondent utilize at moderate extent. Responses view on utilization of ICT for current awareness services in the academic library under study shows that 71(68%) utilized ICT to a low extent, 22(21%) of the respondent were undecided while 10(10%) utilized ICT to a high extent, and 11(10%) utilized ICT to a moderate extent. Items three present responses on utilization of ICT for charging and discharging of materials where 59(57%) utilized with low extent, 22(21%) of the respondent are undecided while 13(12%) of the

respondent utilizing ICT for charging and discharging of materials in the academic library with high extent, and 10(10%) utilized with moderate extent,. Table analysis on extent to you utilize ICT for inter-library loan services where 51(49%) utilized with low extent, 21(20%) utilized with moderate extent 19(18%) of the respondent are undecided while 13(13%) of the respondents utilized with high extent. Finally, the table revealed that 49(47%) of respondents are utilize ICT for user education services in the library at low extent, 17(16%) to a moderate extent while 11(11%) high extent and 27(26%) undecided respectively. This show that majority of the respondent agreed that ICT utilization on service delivery in Academic Libraries were low extent.

Table 3 present the responses on challenges inhibiting service delivery with ICT by librarians in academic libraries where 66(63%) of the respondents indicated yes that ICT

facilities were inadequate while 38(37%) of respondent disagreed that no ICT facilities. Responses view on low level of ICT skills of staff 53(51%) of the respondent said yes that library staff have low level of ICT skills while 51(49%) indicated no. The table analysis on inadequate infrastructure where 91(87%) of the respondents said yes there is adequate infrastructure while 13(13%) no inadequate infrastructure. Items four is on inadequate telecommunication facilities where 89(86%) of the respondents said yes while 15(14%) show their disagreement with the statement. On Staff low level of computer literacy where 78(75%) said yes while 26(21%) said no that staff low level of computer literacy. and on issues of inadequate fund 59(57%) said yes and 45(43%) of the respondents said no that no inadequate funds.

Furthermore, the respond rate on Staff resistance of ICT adoption 71(68%) to be available and 33(32%) not available. Finally, on frequent changes and modification of ICTs 82(79%) of respondents indicated that available while 22(21%) are not available respectively. The result revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that challenges inhibiting service delivery by librarians in academic libraries are frequent change and medication of ICT, low level of ICT skills among librarian, inadequate ICT facilities, and low level of computer literacy.

Discussion of the Findings

Finding on ICT competence of librarians in academic libraries in Adamawa state reflect a low extent of competence. This is in agreement with the study carried out by Atte and Ezra (2016) on essential competencies for effective information service delivery in Nigerian University Libraries, the result shows that, competencies level of the librarians in information technology for the provision of library and information service delivery. It indicates that the respondents were competent

in Microsoft word (words processing skills) with a mean score of 3.4453, e-mail management skills with a mean score of 3.4234 and using an integrated library system (virtual/Alice for windows) have the third highest mean score of 3.3212. It could be said that the respondents are not competent in information technology sampling because majority of the information technology competencies options, respondents were found not to be competent. This implies that they have not been providing library and information service delivery as being expected by their patrons especially in this technological era. It is not surprising because of the dynamic nature of technology which is constantly creating the need for new skills. The study is also in support by Tanloet and Twamsuk (2010) who noted that in order to adopt these developments to library work and catch up with the technological advances, information professionals must learn to acquire various roles, knowledge, competencies and skills. Also, development of professional competencies enables us to work efficiently and survive in the world of libraries and information services. Accordingly, training and retraining of library staff is very essential for effective and efficient library and information service delivery in the Adamawa State Libraries.

Findings on ICT utilization on service delivery in Academic Libraries show low extent. This is in collaboration study carried out by Osuchukwu, Obuezie and Ogwuche (2017) shows that more number of staff utilized ICT facilities weekly and bi-monthly at 56.7%, respectively while 46.6% utilized it weekly and when they have office work. Others are daily utilized at 50% and once a semester at 11%. This shows that greater number of staff utilized the ICT section of the library in Madonna University. A computer performs processing operations on data and is used to store and retrieve information process transaction (charging and discharging), sort, data, etc.

Since the central processing unit (CPU) or the computer has a definitive amount of data capacity; it requires additional storage media, such as magnetic disk and tape, and audio tape. A disk is the most common auxiliary storage device. Telecommunications facilitates the transfer or communication of data and information technology in the libraries. Basically, information technology provides for full organizational structure (i.e. to provide enhanced users satisfaction, cost effectiveness, integration, faster, and simpler programmed, rapid responses, and operational procedures) is not helpful for them, 4.35% respondents have screen reading problems.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that ICT competence of librarians in academic libraries under study reflect low extent and ICT utilization for service delivery in the academic libraries was also utilized with low extent.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations were done:

1. The management of academic libraries in Adamawa State should create awareness on the use of ICT for effective service delivery by the librarians in the libraries under study
2. A lot need to be done by management of academic libraries in Adamawa State for effective utilization of ICT for service delivery.

References

Aba, J., Beetsch, K. & Ogban, O. (2015). The Use of Internet Services by Postgraduate Students for Research in Francis Idachaba Library, University of Agriculture

Makurdi. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5(1), 15-23.

Abbas, K. D. (2014). From Techno-Illiterate to Techno-Literate Era: Nigerian Academic Librarians in Perspective. *International Journal of Humanities & Social Science*. 45(1). Page number

Ademodi, D.T. & Adepoju, E. O. (2019). Computer skills among librarians in academic libraries in Ondo and Ekiti States, Nigeria (LPP274). *Library Philosophy and Practice*.

<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/274>.

Alabi, O. C. & Sani, O. F. (2021). Librarians and Information Service Delivery in Kogi State Nigeria During Covid-19 Pandemic; *Journal of applied Information Science and Technology* .14 (1), 98-109.

Atte, S. L & Ezra, S. G. (2016). Essential Competencies for Effective Information Service Delivery in Nigerian University Libraries. *Journal of Information Manager*, 15(1&2). Page number

Chanchinmawia, F. & Verma, M. K. (2017). Significance of Information Literacy in Digital Environment among Academic Community and Role of Library Professionals, in Ed. Bansal, Vaibhav et.al, *Conjugative management, library information science, social science and technology for virtual world*, New Delhi, 117-122.

Elisha, M. (2006). The Application of Information and Communication Technology (I.C.T.) in Nigerian Academic Libraries: Prospects and Problems. *Information Manager*. 6(1&2), 35-39.

Ikegwuro, P. U. (2017). Application of Internet for Service Delivery in Selected Special Libraries in Kaduna Metropolis. *European Scientific Journal*, 13(7), 411-429.

URL:<http://dx.doi.org/10.19044/esj.2017.v13n7p411>

- Jack, O. (2015). Attitudes toward Computers: When do they Predict Computer use? *Information and Management*. 34(5), 1-12. http://southernlibrarianship.icaap.org/content/v08n02/tella_a01.html.
- Krishnan, Y. (2011). *Twenty first century skills*. Informedia. <http://www.informedlibrarian.com/index.cfm>
- Kwofie, T. E., Aigbavboa, C. & Thwala, W. (2020). Exploring Information and Communications Technology for Enhanced Communication in non-Traditional Procurement. *In Effective Construction Project Delivery* (153-177). Springer, Cham.
- Madu, O. E. (2010). Book Theft and Mutilation and their Effects on the Services of the Benue State Polytechnic Library. *The Electronic Library*, 28(4), 555-567. www.emeraldinsight.com/0264-0473.htm
- Mamman, E. S. (2015). Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTS) in public library services in Nigeria. (A Ph.D. thesis) *Department of Library and Information Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka*.
- Mbofung, U. & Popoola, S.O. (2014). Legal and Ethical Issues of Information Service Delivery and Library Information Science Professionals in University Libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1183>
- Obotu, A. S., Chukwuka, O. O. & Gambo, S. B. (2019). The Need for the Use of Information and Communication Technology in Two University Libraries in Nigeria. incomplete
- Ojiegbe, N. (2010). ICT Competencies of library staff at the university of Abuja FCT and University of Jos, Plateau State [*Unpublished master's dissertation University of Nigeria, Nsukka*]. This source is not needed, you can get the published version or replace it
- Omekwu, C. O. & Echezona, R. I. (2008). Emerging challenges and opportunities for Nigerian libraries in a global information system [*Paper presentation*]. Nigerian Library Association 46th Annual National Conference and AGM, Kaduna. Kaduna State, Nigeria
- Omehia, Anthonia; Okwu, Emmanuel; and Nsirim, Onyema, (2021) "Librarians' ICT Competencies and Utilization of Emerging Technologies in Academic Libraries in Rivers State, Nigeria". *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 5410. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5410>
- Omosor, U. A. & Nelson, E. (2017). The Need for Information Technology in Nigeria Polytechnic Libraries. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(1), 23-27
- Osuchukwu, N. P., Obuezie, A. C. & Ogwuche, G. O. (2017). Availability and Utilization of Information Communication Technology Facilities in a Private University Library in Nigeria. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 8(3), 16-25.
- Oyedokun, T. T. Oyewumi, F. A., Akanbi, M. L. & Laaro, D. M. (2018). Assessment of ICT Perceived Ease of Use to End User Satisfaction with Enterprise Resource

Planning Systems. *Computers in Human Behaviour* 20(4), 505–515.

Partridge, H. L. & Munro, G. (2010). The double helix: A personal account of the discovery of the structure of the information professionals. *Paper presented at ALIA 2004 Biennial Conference, Gold Coast, Australia.* <http://eprints.edu.au/1215>

Tanloet, P. & Twamsuk, K. (2010). Development of core competencies framework for information professional of Thai Academic Libraries in the next decades, (*Doctoral Dissertation Ph.D*) program in information studies, Khon Kaen University, Thailand

Tanawade, M. S. (2011). Effective Interpersonal Skills for Library management. *Indian Streams Research Journal*. 11(1). Page number

Tella A. & Sidiq O. (2017). Interlibrary Loan and Cooperation among Selected Academic Libraries in Kwara State, Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Interlibrary Loan, Document Delivery & Electronic Reserve*, 26(2), 103-120, DOI: 10.1080/1072303X.2017.1386602

Vincent U., Ikonne, C. N. & Ohwofasa, F. (2023). Application of ICT Competence in Library Service Delivery in Public Libraries in South-South, Nigeria. *International Journals of Librarianship* 7(23), 15. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2023.7743>

Zurkowski, P. G. (1974). Information Literacy. National Commission and Information Science: The Information Services Environment Relationships and Priorities. <http://www.eric.ed.gov/PDFS/ED100391.pdf>